

To Save the Republic

The US can correct course through three reasonable measures, which would be taken by all US citizens, and the world, as the sure sign that the Union will persevere.

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Summary

If the Constitution and federal law continues to be semantically weaponised, then the Republic is lost.

The US can correct course through three reasonable measures, which would be taken by all US citizens, and the world, as the sure sign that the Union will persevere. To save the Republic, the Biden-Harris administration must:

1. Decisively end authoritarianism by disbanding the Republican Party through Trial
2. Decisively end neoliberalism by disbanding the Democratic Party through Constitutional Convention
3. Restart the US via Debt Jubilee

I. Trial

The US needs to prosecute the Republican core, showing the world what will happen to the enablers of the next authoritarian figurehead.

This trial needs to be a performative assertion of the health of the Republic, to the fullest and highest degree.

The Republicans acted against the health of the Republic, pursuing short-term political advantages. This caused a metastasis of self-seeking behaviors by individuals in the government, such as the 45th President.

The prosecution of such individuals is not the goal of this trial. The Republican Party and its collaborators are the defendants. The charge is pocide, i.e. treason.

Seemingly mistaking Tacitus' *Annals* for *The Federalist Papers*, the Republican party made a Roman gamble, and now must pay a Roman price:

This trial must decisively end authoritarianism in the US by disbanding the Republican Party.

Every procedural hole, all those aspects of governance that (it's now abundantly clear) require good faith, that Republicans have exploited, must become a penitentiary gate for those who walked through them.

This trial has to reach all the way down to AG William Barr's collaborators at state levels. A Republic in which the AG organises police chiefs, who in turn organise armed militias against the political opposition, is clearly in constitutional crisis.

A reasonable indicator that this trial has taken the full measure of the gravity of the situation will be that indicted public servants serve time in facilities directed and staffed by more recent immigrants and people of color.

Avoiding Disunion

Such a trial will cause a percentage of the 72 million Americans who recently signed off on the Republican's pocide to go postal.

A NYT exit poll found that over 80% of those 72 million do not believe climate change is a serious threat.

To paraphrase Fintan O'Toole [1](#), half of the voting population has reverted to a pre-democratic state.

The reasons for this reversion can only be meaningfully addressed by a constitutional convention, through which the Democratic Party will perforce be disbanded.

Before this can occur, the authoritarian formations of disordered power, which both victimise and are called into being by the pre-democratic population, must first be disbanded.

Under a functional Constitution and federal system, let alone under current existential risks, such authoritarian formations of disordered power cannot be permitted by any legitimate US government.

The US government must face what this means:

If a drowning person is in a mental state that causes them to attack the lifeguard, a traditional rescue attempt would mean the lifeguard is recklessly endangering their own life, and hence their protective responsibility.

If a person with severe COVID-19 is in a mental state (through propaganda, not COVID dementia, the resemblance of their effects notwithstanding) that causes them to attack their caregivers, right up to the point of intubation², then the liability for reckless endangerment falls on the propagandists.

If a person with COVID-19 goes out in public and willfully seeks to infect others with the virus, then the liability that falls on propagandists escalates to manslaughter or worse³.

If we are talking not about one person, but a sizable percentage of 72 million people -

- and two tidal waves, one economic and one pandemic, have crested the horizon -

- then the cascade of criminal liability has reached wartime levels⁴.

The US government must face what this means, and face it right now. Taking a figurative lesson from the California fires, this tinder needs to be burned, in a controlled fire, before the inevitable next wave of authoritarianism.

The moment for this controlled burn, via the trial that disbands the Republican Party, is right now. This trial will by itself trigger the overdue Constitutional Convention.

II. Constitutional Convention

The Constitutional Convention triggered by the trial does not have the goal of adjusting the Constitution as it stands, in an attempt to return to a previous form of stable governance.

The framers based the US Constitution on their study of how previous Republics arose and fell.

This first goal of this convention is to repeat this study, as a national/global digital chautauqua on Collapsology. This focus encompasses climate change, elite overproduction, inequality, negative compounding / black swans, and negatively synergistic risks / syndemics.

The second goal is to restructure the US to most effectively counter the risks of collapse. The core of this is the dismantling of neoliberalism and a decisive and long-lasting solution to economic inequality. This means the disbanding of elites, hence the disbanding of the Democratic Party.

To centrist arguments for the impossibility of this under a Democratic administration: this is not a statement of a given political mechanism, this is a statement of performative necessity.

The Biden-Harris administration must perform the disbanding of the Republican Party by trial, and then perform the disbanding of the Democratic Party.

The Republican Party substituted Tacitus' *Annals* for *The Federalist Papers*. The Democratic Party must in turn substitute *The Oresteia*.

What the Biden-Harris administration must perform, is the restaging of the Republican's Roman tragedy - through which the social order further decays - into a Greek tragedy, through which the social order is restored.

III.

Debt Jubilee

The trial will trigger the Constitutional Convention.

The Constitutional Convention will result in the Debt Jubilee.

A debt jubilee is necessary to end the entrenched domination of the rentier class. As the economic history of the last ten thousand years makes abundantly

clear, a dominant rentier class crashing a society is the default. We've been here many times before.

The guillotine was invented to humanely kill rentiers during a revolution. We must performatively end neoliberalism by shredding the monopoly money and the Landlord Game rules now⁵. Failing to do so with due haste must be taken to incur liability for escalating political violence followed by disunion.

Postscript

Can a Republic consciously collapse?

Can a society consciously die, so that it can be reborn?

Is this a Greek or a Roman tragedy?

A disaster through which the social order is restored, or through which it further decays?

The American Republic suffered under the American Empire, was crucified, died, and was buried.

Does it rise again on the third day, or was that just a story?

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1. <https://www.nybooks.com/articles/2020/12/03/democracys-afterlife/> ↩
 2. This has been happening:
<https://twitter.com/JodiDoering/status/1327771331920883714> ↩
 3. This keeps happening as well:
<https://www.newson6.com/story/5e7e3ac1065c486efd6d14f6/people-intentionally-spreading-covid19-infecting-others-could-face-federal-charges> ↩
 4. 'A general effect of war is that in its aftermath there is a period of endemic grift that is hard to root out until you restart broad-based wealth building somehow. We've been in an invisible war for several years based on the rising grift levels.'
- <https://twitter.com/vgr/status/1326589319172169729> ↩

5. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/The_Landlord%27s_Game↩

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